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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN
LIPID PROFILE AND PLATELETS PARAMETERS AND
RAISED PLATELETS RELATION WITH HEART DISEASES**¹Dr Nabhan Ahmed ²Dr Shoaib Khalid ³Dr Shayan Idrees³Shalamar Medical and Dental College Lahore²Demonstrator in Pathology, Avicenna Medical College, Lahore¹Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: Increasing plasma low density lipoprotein levels is an important risk factor for early onset of heart disease and atherosclerosis.

Aim: The aim of this study is to assess the correlation between lipid profile and platelets parameters of blood donors and to find out the association of platelet volume indices with heart diseases.

Place and Duration: In the Medicine Unit II of Lahore General Hospital for six months duration from September 2019 to February 2020.

Material and method: A cross-sectional study was conducted among blood donors (n = 80) from the Faculty of Medicine. The medical history of blood donors was taken using a questionnaire, and lipid levels were analyzed using blood samples.

Results: Of the 80 blood samples, 30 had hyperlipidemia and 50 had normolipidemia. Statistical significance of age and sex mass ($p = 0.05$) in hyperlipidemic groups. Platelet parameters were also significantly higher in hyperlipidemic groups, and a significant relationship was found between hyperlipidemia based on donor weight and platelet parameters ($p = 0.05$).

Conclusion: High platelet volume indices increase the risk of hyperlipidemic heart disease. Other tests should be observed on larger samples.

Key words: platelet volume indices, hyperlipidemia, atherosclerosis, lipid levels

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INTRODUCTION:

Hyperlipidemia is an important risk factor for the early onset of coronary heart disease, especially high plasma levels of low density lipoprotein (LDL), atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease. Low density lipoprotein (LDL) and platelets are thought to be a risk factor for developing heart disease. Oxidized LDL (oxLDL) has been shown to increase platelet aggregation by increasing susceptibility to agonists and by reducing the expression and activity of nitric oxide (NO) synthase in platelets. Activated platelets secrete protein as a factor stimulating the absorption of oxLDL by macrophages. With the help of automated hematology analyzers, platelet counts and platelet volume indexes (PVI) can easily be obtained in many clinical laboratories at no extra charge. Based on these indicators, a close relationship with hyperlipidemia can be established, which can be demonstrated by a slight change in platelet size. These indicators can be used as an early, cost-effective identification of heart disease and may be predictors of heart disease risk than a single serum lipid value (e.g. Tchol, HDL or LDL). In this study, the study aimed to assess the correlation between the lipid profile of blood donors and platelet parameters, and to investigate the relationship between platelet volume indices and heart disease. Exclusion criteria will be introduced to increase the safety of donor selection and blood transfusion by testing hyperlipidemia in blood donors and linking them to platelet parameters.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross-sectional study was conducted among blood donors (n = 80) at the Medicine Unit II of Lahore General Hospital for six months duration from September 2019 to February 2020. The medical history of blood donors was taken during donation. Informed written consent was obtained from each participant, and the audit report was approved by the corporate ethics committee. The study covered people aged 18-65.

Admission Criteria

Criteria for inclusion in the selection of patients: hemoglobin level > 12.5 gm / dl and weight 45 kg or more, pulse rate: 60 to 100 per minute and regular, blood pressure: systolic 100-180 mm Mercury; diastolic 50-100 mm hours

Exclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria are donors who have been transfused within 6 months or transferred within 3 months. People taking medications such as a known heart problem, endocrine disorder, thyroid disorder, diabetes (in insulin therapy), hypertension, NSAIDs, steroids and anti-cancer drugs were also excluded from the study. The questionnaire was used to record general information. After collecting the blood in the amount of 350 ml, 5 ml of blood was taken into a single vial, after centrifugation, the serum was separated and various lipid parameters were assessed using a fully automated analyzer (TRIGL: triglycerides, LDL-C: cholesterol). LDL plus 2nd generation, CHOL 2: Cholesterol Gen 2, HDL-C3: HDL-Cholesterol plus 3rd generation, diagnosis Cobas C311-Roche Chi-square and p-value were evaluated to determine the compound.

RESULTS:

The study included 80 blood donors; 30 of them had hyperlipidemia, 22 of them were men and 8 were women. Donors were between 18 and 65 years old. Cases showed a significant relationship between lipid levels and platelet parameters compared to controls. The results are summarized in the table because 30 of 80 blood samples were hyperlipidemic and 50 were normolipidemic. There were significant differences in hyperlipidemic groups in terms of sex (p <0.05), age and body weight. Platelet parameters, including platelet count and platelet volume indices (MPV, PDW and P-CSF) were significantly higher in hyperlipidemic groups and a significant association was found between hyperlipidemia based on donor weight. and platelet parameters (p <0.05) These results showed that platelet parameters were significantly higher in hyperlipidemic blood donors (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1 Distribution of gender, weight and age of blood donors with respect to hyperlipidemia

Parameters		Hyperlipidemia (n=30)	Chi-square (χ^2)	p-value (≤ 0.05 : significant*, ≤ 0.001 : highly significant**)
Gender	Male	22	6.53	0.030*
	Female	8		
Age	18-25 years	10	7.20	0.020*
	26-45 years	16		
	46-65 years	4		
Weight	50-70 kg	24	10.80	0.004*
	Above 70 kg	6		

Table 2 Correlation between weights, lipid profile and platelet parameters in hyperlipidemia

Weight	Lipid Profile (T chol, TG, HDL, and LDL)	Platelet Parameters (Platelet count and Platelet Volume Indices: platelet distribution width, platelet large cell ratio and mean platelet volume,		Chisquare (χ^2)	p-value ($\leq$ 0.05:significant*, $\leq$ 0.001:highly significant**)
		Normal	Abnormal		
>70 Kg	Hyperlipidemia	1	23	4.53	0.03*
50-70 Kg	Hyperlipidemia	2	4		

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 23 statistics (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). To find out the relationship, a chi square was estimated and a p value of $P < 0.05$ was used to show statistically significant results.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Despite their role in the formation of platelets after plaque rupture in late atherosclerosis, platelets are believed to be the initiator of the atherosclerotic process. Hyperlipidemia has abnormalities in the composition and function of platelets, which indicates that circulating lipoproteins in the blood affect the properties of platelets. In fact, there is growing evidence that lipoproteins affect platelet function. Oxidized LDL (LDLD), especially those containing apoprotein B-100, are atherogenic lipoproteins and increase antiplatelet activation, while increasing platelet activation, interestingly, in vitro data, platelets can be activated by LDL, and HDL can be anesthetized with HDL. which emphasizes anti-atherosclerotic properties. Large platelets tend to be more metabolically active than small platelets and release more thrombotic agents. Platelet volume indices reflect platelet reactivity and have been proposed as a risk factor for ischemic events in cardiovascular disease. Many studies have shown that the increase in MPV is associated with many diseases such as coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction, cerebral infarction and diabetes. In this study, we found that the hyperlipidemic group had significantly higher MPV values. Larger platelets are more biologically active, and thrombotic factors are higher, therefore they are an important risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Our data showed that the hyperlipidemic group had significantly higher MPV, PDW and P-CSF. This finding is consistent with the results of many previous studies. PDW is a specific marker for platelet activation because it does not increase during normal platelet edema. In our study, MPV, PDW and P-CSF were significantly higher in hyperlipidemic blood donors and there was a significant correlation between PVI and lipid profile. Platelets with hyperlipidemia may be more cumulative and reactive due to increased PVI. High PVI levels with hyperlipidemia may be a risk factor for atherosclerosis in adults. These indicators can

be used as an early, cost-effective identification of heart disease and may be predictors of heart disease risk than a single serum lipid value (e.g. Tchol, HDL or LDL). The increased risk of atherosclerosis in adults with hyperlipidemia may be due to high platelet volume indexes (PVI). These indicators can be used for the early, cost-effective and rapid identification of coronary risk factors, as well as to explain the pattern of platelet activation in the progression of hyperlipidemia, and therefore should be included in donor delay criteria. It can be used to set exclusion criteria when selecting a transmitter. Therefore, it will help patients with more stringent delay and donor criteria to improve blood circulation and allow blood banks to provide safe blood and improve blood safety guidelines.

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